

An interpretative Framework for Operationalization of Extremist Narrative Analysis

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A short introduction to important concepts of the framework

Extremist Narratives are meaning-making systems that structure events by framing the involved actors in a morally superior in-group that problematizes a dangerous and morally inferior out-group. This framing serves to justify, either implicitly or explicitly, particular actions or solutions directed toward the perceived threat (Postigo Fuentes et al. 2024).

The interpretative framework for the analysis of extremist narratives is designed as a tool to systematically identify the narrative building blocks and assess the extent to which the identified narrative presents an extremist stance. In this respect, the elements of the narrative schema can be stacked, thus highlighting the link between individual narrative schemas and the overarching meta-narrative. Moreover, the framework allows to pin down the elements regardless of whether they are stated explicitly or conveyed implicitly through the (wide) context.

Although we are currently working on expanding the concept of narrative circulation and its relationship with concepts such as mainstreaming or legitimisation, we publish this framework first and foremost as a tool to study the structure of extremist narratives. However, the framework also allows to study one of the crucial aspects of extremist narratives, i.e. their circulation – which we understand as the ‘transfer of narratives from one social and cultural field to another’ (Herman and Vervaeck 2019, 270), based on a complex process of reproduction and renewal (Boch et al. 2009). Reproduction consists of the simple reuse of the narrative told, while renewal includes the creative recycling of its content and structure. The application of the framework to the analysis of the circulation is, however, currently a work in progress and will be covered in a journal paper which we are preparing.

This reflects the understanding that the description of extremist narratives necessarily includes a two-layer approach. At the core of an extremist narrative lies the deep narrative structure, which this framework enables to identify. Surrounding this is the expressive or aesthetic layer which captures the mutable features of the narrative’s realization—its tone, genre, platform, visual or stylistic form, and makes the circulation of narratives possible in different contexts. These features are not systematically included in our framework, but can be specified once the narrative structure is identified.

One of the main strengths of the framework is its adaptability to different contexts. For this reason, we use the term ‘users’ to describe individuals engaging with the framework broadly, rather than limiting it to the academic sphere by using, for example, ‘researchers’. This choice reflects our belief that the framework can serve as a tool not only for analysis and research but also for practitioners such as teachers and policymakers, and other stakeholders who engage with narratives in their professional contexts.

The framework

The framework for the identification and interpretation of extremist narratives relates three levels that allow for the identification of the fundamental narrative elements on the one hand, and for the interpretation of extremist stance on the other hand. The three levels include:

- the group identity level which consists of the following elements: in-group, out-group, the relationship between them and the position of the narrator;
- the thesis level which is related to problem identification and includes the following elements: problematization and perspective; and
- the solution level which includes, as the element, the preferred solution of the problem expressed at the thesis level.

Figure 1 presents the framework schematically, depicting all crucial elements for identifying extremist narratives. These elements are shown as interconnected and relatively mobile. Interconnectedness is illustrated through the lines that connect the elements, and through the big square box representing the *perspective*. With this visualization, we aim to highlight the importance of identifying each of the elements and we want to emphasize the mutual influence and potential overlap between the elements. We are aware that *perspective* is an aspect linked to discourse analysis and requires a greater knowledge of the context.

Similarly, the connecting lines and overlapping boxes reflect the framework's mobility, as they visually represent that the elements can be positioned closer together or farther apart. More specifically, the furthest the elements are from the centre, the more difference between the actors, the more alarming the problem and the more violent the solution; hence the more extremist the narrative (see Section 1.4). This mobility of framework elements showcases the adaptability of narratives which can address varying degrees of extremism and align with different overarching narratives.

Figure 1: The interpretative framework for the analysis of extremist narratives. Self-produced figure

As mentioned above, the elements depicted in Figure 1 are grouped into three levels that lay the foundation for identifying extremist narratives. However, we understand that these three levels may be too abstract to provide a sufficiently robust structure to ensure that research is reliable, rigorous, and consistently interpretable across different contexts and methodologies. For this reason, we have developed a semi-closed set of values for the relevant elements of the framework that should be identified in the interpretation process. The suggested values (listed and explained below and in the appendix) have been drawn from related works (Forti 2024; Baider and Gregoriou 2024; Wodak 2021; Wilson and Hainsworth 2012) and from our own pilot studies, but any such list is necessarily insufficient. For this reason, the appendix should be used only as a list of suggestions to be adapted to the research context and user needs. Below, we focus our attention on the three levels and their elements that enable the identification of extremist narratives.

1.1 - The group identity level

The group identity level allows us to pin down the existence of the Us/Them dichotomy, and when present, specify the exact relationship between the two groups (Table 1). The groups can be referred to explicitly, usually the case with the out-group, or implicitly, usually the case with the in-group. In cases where emphasis is placed on or the case of a particular person is used, as occurs in storytelling (Postigo-Fuentes et al., 2024), we understand that that person acts as a representative of the entire group. In such cases, the referents are identified as groups.

The values for in-group and out-group are listed in the Appendix, and are the same for the in-/out-group. The reason for this is that the in-/out-group identity is not integral to a specific group, but is created only inside a particular narrative. It should be added that in some cases, the in-/out-group are obscured to such a level in the discourse, that they cannot be named with confidence. In such cases, where nonetheless the existence of the dichotomy is clear, a special value (*Unclear*) can be used. This is important because the Us/Them dichotomy is an essential building block of extremist narratives. Therefore, the user needs to be clear about the cases in which the in-/out-group are present but cannot be defined versus the cases where the Us/Them dichotomy cannot be established.

The in-group is the collective that the narrator seeks to protect or champion. It is typically portrayed as homogenous and morally superior. The in-group is presented as embodying positive qualities, often depicted as being under threat by the out-group. It is worth mentioning that more general groups like *men*, *women* or *children*, could often be a sub-group of other categories like *true Spanish women*, *'real' traditional men* -opposing to any new form of masculinity- or *children* only born to native parents. It is also important to note that the narrator is not necessarily part of the in-group.

The out-group represents the antagonistic force in the narrative, often depicted as inferior, dangerous, or morally corrupt. This group is frequently blamed for societal problems or threats to the in-group. Examples of out-groups include immigrants, feminist, scientists/academics, or globalist powers.

The framework proposes a separate value to determine whether the narrator is part of the in-group or not. The reason for this is that the narrator plays a pivotal role in conveying the extremist narrative. Often, the narrator positions themselves outside the in-group to lend credibility and an air of objectivity to the narrative. For narratological reasons, the narrator might use a group other than themselves—such as 'the children'—as the in-group, portraying them as victims of and morally superior to the out-group. However, there are instances where the narrator includes themselves within the in-group, directly aligning their perspective with that of the group they aim to defend or promote.

The identification of the referents is crucial because they serve as concrete anchorage points that position the narrative in a particular discourse. By identifying the specific in-/out-group and considering the naming choices used to signify the two groups, the narratives are given a particular communication context that make them plausible and thus crucially contribute to its persuasiveness for the readership. Moreover, evoking a given Us/Them dichotomy in the narrative is a constitutive act in its own right, since the narrative creates/reproduces a particular vision of reality.

ELEMENT	SUB-ELEMENT	QUESTION	VALUES
In-group		Who is the central group opposed to the out-group?	A list of suggested values is provided in the Appendix.
Out-group		Who is the in-group's opponent?	A list of suggested values is provided in the Appendix.
Narrator		Does the narrator belong to the specified in-group or not?	Yes; No.
Relationship		What is the relationship between the in-group and out-group based on?	Superiority_or_Inferiority; Criticism/disagreement without superiority/inferiority slant; Praise/Agreement without superiority/inferiority slant; Indirect endorsement; Unclear.
	Superiority type	What is the argumentative basis of the superiority - inferiority relationship?	Victimization of In-group; Enemization of Out-group; Heroic past of the In-group; Hopeful future thanks to the In-group; Catastrophic ending due to Out-group; Other positive stereotyping of In-group; Other negative stereotyping of Out-group

Table 1: The elements and values at the group identity level.

While the Us/Them dichotomy is essential in identifying extremist narratives, the relationship between the two groups is one of the important aspects that help us understand the level of extremism of a particular narrative. The power dynamics between the in-group and out-group are crucial to understanding the structure and impact of extremist narratives. These dynamics can manifest in various forms, influencing the tone and direction of the narrative.

The framework suggests five values to describe power dynamics, namely (1) Superiority_or_Inferiority; (2) Criticism/disagreement without superiority/inferiority slant; (3) Praise/Agreement without superiority/inferiority slant; (4) Indirect endorsement and (5) Unclear.

The crucial one, from the perspective of extremist narratives, is the relationship of superiority or Inferiority between the two groups. This dynamic explicitly or implicitly suggests that one group is superior or inferior to another, and is divided into several specific types. These types help the user better understand the argumentative basis on which the extremist narrative is built, because they reveal how the narrative manipulates emotions, perceptions, and group identities to establish a clear 'Us/Them' dynamic. Understanding these types allows users to uncover the rhetorical strategies extremists use to polarize audiences, reinforce loyalty within the in-group, and create a sense of urgency or moral justification for conflict.

We propose seven types of the Superiority_or_Inferiority power dynamics between the in-group and the out-group (it is possible to identify more than one type in the same statement):

- Victimization of the In-Group: The in-group is portrayed as unjustly suffering, reinforcing its moral superiority.
- Enemization of the Out-Group: The out-group is depicted as a dangerous enemy.
- Heroic Past of the In-Group: The in-group's history is glorified, suggesting a legacy of greatness.
- Hopeful Future Thanks to the In-Group: The in-group is depicted as the saviour capable of bringing about a better future.
- Catastrophic Ending Due to the Out-Group: The narrative warns of doom if the out-group is not opposed.
- Other Positive Stereotyping of the In-Group: Generalized positive traits are attributed to the in-group.
- Other Negative Stereotyping of the Out-Group: Negative traits are generalized to the out-group.

As mentioned earlier, there can also exist other types of power dynamics between the in-/out-group in addition to the relationship based on a perception of superiority/inferiority. The framework proposes three additional values to determine this relationship.

First, the in-/out-group can be in a relationship of Indirect Endorsement. In these cases, the statement subtly reinforces division or polarization and indirectly aligns with extremist narratives. Although it is clear that the perception of superiority/inferiority is not expressed to an extent to allow for this value attribution, the statement nonetheless propagates a narrative of division by subtly echoing or legitimizing extremist viewpoints. This dynamic is particularly important to analyse because it operates below the surface level, allowing extremist narratives to spread or gain acceptance without overtly extremist language thereby facilitating their normalization and gradual integration into mainstream discourse. By normalizing divisive rhetoric or framing extremist positions as plausible, it paves the way for a more clearly established dynamics of superiority/inferiority and more explicitly stated extremist content.

Second, the in-/out-group can be in a relationship of Criticism/Disagreement Without Superiority/Inferiority Slant. In some narratives, the in-group (member) may criticize or disagree with the out-group without implying an inherent superiority or inferiority. This type of interaction suggests

that the power hierarchy is not central to the argument. The disagreement may be based on differences in opinion, policy, or approach, but the narrative does not position one group as fundamentally better or worse than the other.

Third, the in-/out-group can be in a relationship of Praise/Agreement Without Superiority/Inferiority Slant. There are instances where the narrative includes praise or agreement without emphasizing a power hierarchy. Here, the in-group may express endorsement or empathy towards the out-group, recognizing common ground or shared values. This type of narrative interaction can occur in contexts where cooperation or understanding between the groups is highlighted, rather than conflict or division.

And finally, the in-/out-group can be in a Neutral/Unclear relationship. Some narratives may present general statements, observations, or personal impressions that do not clearly link to the out-group or are ambiguous in their relationship to it. In these cases, the narrative might not clearly establish a power relation or may omit the out-group entirely, focusing instead on broader or more abstract ideas. Due to this neutrality or lack of clarity, such narratives cannot be identified as extremist, however they still convey a particular world view and can therefore be influential in shaping perceptions through subtler means.

1.2. - The thesis level

The thesis level incorporates three elements: problematization, variation and perspective (Table 2), and is dedicated to the identification of the central problem that is perceived as being causally related to the out-group. Acting as the core catalyst of the narrative, this particular problem leads to the consequences the narrator seeks to highlight as a threat or risk to the in-group.

The framework suggests a two-tier identification of the problem incorporating problematization and variation. The element of problematization focuses on identifying the general level problem that the narrative highlights. The problematization could revolve around issues like safety, economics, culture, or social rights. For example, the narrative might frame the out-group as a physical threat to the in-group’s safety or as an economic burden that endangers the in-group’s well-being. In a similar way, not the threat, but the risk of any kind of danger for the in-group could also be considered a type of problematization.

The second tier is problem variation. It is used to describe the specific forms of the perceived problem/threat. For instance, within the context of safety, the narrative might warn of risks like rape, robbery, terrorist attacks or murder associated with the out-group. These variations add specificity to the narrative, making the problem appear more critical, imminent and tangible.

The final element to define at the thesis level is the perspective. This element uncovers the underlying ideology driving the narrative. The ideological perspective could range from religious integralism to ethnonationalism, heteronormativity and so on. These ideologies frame the narrative, providing the rationale for the in-group’s perceived moral superiority and the out-group’s inherent threatening character. Defining the perspective alongside the specific and general problem, allows the user to discern the particular position from which the expressed problematization is coherent with the rest of the narratological elements. In this sense, the same problematization can stem from different motivating perspectives.

ELEMENT	SUB-ELEMENT	QUESTION	VALUES
Problematization		What does the narrative establish as the crucial general problem linked to the	A list of suggested values is provided in the Appendix.

		out-group?	
	Variation	What does the narrative establish as the specific problem linked to the out-group?	A list of suggested values is provided in the Appendix.
Perspective		Which seems to be the primary ideological perspective motivating the narrator?	A list of suggested values is provided in the Appendix.

Table 2: The elements and values at the thesis level.

1.3 - The solution level

The solution level is concerned with the implicitly or explicitly suggested solution to the problem identified at the thesis level. This framework proposes annotating the solution in terms of the kind of proposed action, rather than listing actual specific actions. This decision aligns with the goal of using the framework as a tool to measure the degree of extremist rhetoric within a statement. The extremism level is evaluated by considering the perceived threat to the survival of the out-group, with the most violent and harmful proposed solutions being categorized as the most extreme.

The framework operates with the following kinds of solutions that can be explicit or implicit:

- Call to violence/violence: The statement explicitly or implicitly calls for or endorses violent actions as a reaction to the problem.
- Radicalization/Call to group consolidation: The statement calls for group consolidation and suggests common action as the only way to success.
- Protest/Civil disobedience without clear violence incitement: The statement calls for non-violent but public action/manifestation to try to acquire the implementation of the desired solution.
- Prohibition/Silencing/Dismissal/Expulsion/Undefined action to address the threat: The statement proposes restrictive, exclusionary and discriminatory actions that are intended to address the threat.
- No proposed solution: The statement does not suggest any possible solution or may be totally fatalistic.

The narrative can, although not necessarily, culminate in a proposed solution to the problem or threat posed by the out-group. In some cases, no solution is stated or clearly implied, leaving the narrative in a state of fatalism where the threat is portrayed as insurmountable. This does not mean that the narrative does not include a possible solution at all, just that the statement itself does not give clear indicators as to what kind of action is preferred by the narrator as a solution to the problem caused by the out-group. In such cases, the framework presumes that no solution is proposed in order to discourage overinterpretation.

ELEMENT	QUESTION	VALUES
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Solution	What is the suggested solution to the problem?	Call to violence/violence; Radicalization/Call to group consolidation; Protest/Civil disobedience without clear violence incitement; Prohibition/Silencing/Dismissal/Expulsion/Undefined action to address the threat; No proposed solution
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Table 3: The element and values at the solution level.

1.4 - Defining the spectrum of extremism in narratives

As explained above, extremist narratives are marked by their portrayal of a rigid dichotomy between an in-group, which is depicted as morally superior and legitimate, and an out-group, which is framed as dangerous, inferior, and an existential threat. However, the degree of this rigidity is not fixed but exists on a spectrum. It is determined by two factors: (a) at the group identity level, the framework identifies the level of extremism by looking at the level of rigidity and hostility of the relationship between the in-group and the out-group, and (b) at the solution level, the framework focuses on the identification of the degree of extremism on the harm potential for the out-group.

Extremist representation of the groups' identity is not static: in-group and out-group identities may be shifted over time in response to evolving crises, ideological recalibrations, and strategic needs. As certain in-groups seek to sustain their relevance, they may redefine their enemies, incorporate new grievances, or adjust their self-perception to align with changing narratives. This fluidity ensures that extremist discourse remains adaptable, continuously reconfiguring the Us/Them dichotomy to maintain cohesion and mobilization. Moreover, the rigidity is influenced also by the relationship the in-group has towards the in-between group, which is a critical battleground for influence. Extremist narratives strategically frame this in-between group as either a potential ally of the in-group or as complicit with the out-group. This flexibility allows narratives to adapt their reach, recruiting, radicalizing, or isolating individuals and groups based on context. Regardless of these shifts, the narratives remain rooted in an ideological rigidity that rejects negotiation and reinforces polarization by dismissing any middle ground.

The proposed solutions within extremist narratives also contribute to the placement of the claim on the spectrum of extremism. At the most extreme end, narratives advocate for physical violence, presenting it as essential for the in-group's survival. Less overtly violent approaches emphasize radicalization or group consolidation to actively resist perceived threats. Moderate strategies suggest civil disobedience, protests, or exclusionary measures such as silencing, banning, or expelling the out-group. Some narratives, however, fail to propose a feasible or any solution at all, fostering a sense of inevitable doom and leaving their audience in a state of fatalistic resignation. Across these variations, the narrative consistently emphasizes the in-group's legitimacy and moral imperative to act, reinforcing the uncompromising stance that defines extremism.

While this framework centers on the internal structure of extremist narratives, it is important to acknowledge that such narratives may appear in a range of communicative settings, including those often described as "mainstream." This may occur through two related dynamics (Brown et al. 2023) : first, the mainstreamization of narratives once considered marginal, a process through which the

normative boundaries of public discourse shift over time; and second, the strategic or incidental appearance of extremist narratives within mainstream discourse, even if they remain contested or temporary. In both cases, the presence of such narratives in the mainstream underscores the need for a structural analytic approach that focuses on narrative logic — how problems are framed, groups are constructed, and solutions proposed — rather than on the status of the speaker or the platform.

Seeing extremist narratives as existing on a spectrum, is crucial to understanding their adaptability and impact. These narratives effectively polarize and mobilize audiences, entrenching divisions and solidifying the in-group’s position as morally superior and justified in its hostility. Identifying these dynamics is key for dismantling the influence of extremist narratives and fostering more inclusive and negotiable discourses.

APPENDIX

This appendix provides a non-exhaustive list of values for the categories of the framework. The values can be freely added as well as their scope enlarged or reduced as seen fit by the user of the framework. For the explanation of the framework, please refer to the paper.

US/THEM DICHOTOMY: the in-group and the out-group

In-group is the social group which is seen positively or endangered by the existence/activity of the outgroup. Often, although not necessarily always, the narrator identifies with the in-group. Out-group is the social group with which the narrator does not identify or which is endangering the in-group. In the identification of the in-group/out-group, the user should try to find or formulate a name that most closely describes the actors as referenced in the utterance, and not already as interpreted by the user of the framework, e.g., a group might be interpreted as anti-feminist men, but might be presented in the utterance in a generalised manner as men. Since the identification of the actors should be based on the references found in the utterance, the proposed values can be used both for the in-group and the out-group.

VALUE	DESCRIPTION
Men	Men when used as a generalised, homogenous group.
Women	Women when used as a generalised, homogenous group.
Children	Minors when used as a generalised, homogenous group.
Family/parents	The basic social unit consisting of parents and children when the family/parents are used as an entity (regardless of sexual orientation).
Immigrants/Asylum seekers	People who move to another country seeking refuge or better opportunities.
Jewish people	Individuals belonging to the Jewish faith or ethnicity.

Romani people	Ethnic group traditionally known as travelers.
Muslims	Followers of Islam.
Christians	Followers of Christianity.
Other religion	Individuals practising religions other than those that have separate tags.
Europe	The continent of Europe understood historically as the center of the world.
Own nation/country	The specific country of reference, seen as a source of identity and pride.
Other nation//country	The specific country of reference, seen as foreign to the national identity.
NGO/activists/social movements	Non-governmental organizations/individuals, often involved in humanitarian or advocacy work aiming to bring social change
People	General populace, often used to denote the ordinary citizens or masses.
Politicians/political party	Elected officials and governmental bodies.
Government	The ruling authority of a state.
Opposition	Political parties or groups that challenge and critique the government, offering alternative policies and holding it accountable.
National democratic institutions	Referred to the democratic system of a particular country, in particular pertains to the legal system and judiciary, including courts, judges, and legal proceeding
Business/Private sector	Commercial enterprises and the corporate sector.
Public sector	Government-run and funded services and organisations. This includes the judicial branch.
School staff	Employees working within educational institutions.

Media/Journalists	News outlets and reporters.
Scientists/Academics	Individuals involved in scientific research and higher education.
EU institutions/political individuals	Entities or individuals involved in European governance and policy.
EU	European union as union of countries.
Supranational global actors	International organisations like the World Health Organization.
LGBTQIA+	Individuals who identify as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, asexual, and other non-heteronormative identities.
Feminists	People who support gender equality and women's rights.
Communists	Individuals or groups advocating for economic communist ideologies and policies. To be used only when the utterance refers to the economic aspects, otherwise, i.e. when social system is meant in more general terms, Cultural Marxist should be used.
Environmentalist	Individuals advocating for the protection of nature.
Patriots/nationalists	Individuals referred to as overly nationalistic or xenophobic.
Neo-fascist/neo-Nazi group/individual	Limited to cases where the individual/group is (self)-referenced as such.
Cultural Marxist	Limited to cases where the individual/group is referenced as supporters of cultural marxism which is a narrative where communism is not limited to an economic ideology but encompasses a supposed agenda of “wokeness” or eco-marxism. This agenda includes elements such as multiculturalism, seen as a threat to cultural homogeneity and traditional values; progressivism, representing any initiative or idea that promotes social change or justice; and cancel culture, perceived as an attack on freedom of expression and traditions. Cultural Marxism is usually presented as a sort of clandestine movement seeking to destroy moral values and traditional European societies. This narrative argues that progressive forces are infiltrating all areas of society to weaken national identity and social cohesion. The fight against this enemy is seen as a battle for the survival of the nation and its fundamental values. In that context, modern anti-communism, or simply anti-Marxism, is articulated as a defence against a vast conspiracy that seeks to uproot traditional values

	through the promotion of progressive ideas. In this framework, any movement advocating for equality, social justice, or cultural diversity is demonised as part of a larger plot to undermine Western civilization. According to this narrative, the enemies of the nation not only include traditional communists but also a wide variety of progressive and liberal groups.
Science Sceptics	Individuals or groups skeptical of the mainstream scientific consensus, including vaccination sceptics and climate change deniers.
Science absolutist	Individuals who believe science should not be questioned.
Anti-feminists/anti-LGBTIQ+	Including incels/misogynists and opponents to feminist positions.
Conspiracy theorist	Individuals seen as promoting dangerous misinformation.
Globalist Powers/the Elites	Entities/individuals are referenced as those undermining national sovereignty and local cultures, like Soros, Gates, the economic elites, which are often used by conspiracy theorists. This tag includes national elites that are seen as working against the nation.
Undefined/Unclear	Ambiguous or undefined groups or positions.
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THESIS

The thesis level incorporates three aspects: problematization, variation and perspective, and is dedicated to the identification of the central problem that is perceived as being causally related to the out-group on the one hand, and to the interpretative angle adopted by the producer on the other hand.

Problematization

This category delves into the specific problematization described by the text in a particular potentially extremist narrative.

VALUE	DESCRIPTION
Safety	The utterance centres the problem described in its narrative on anything related to physical safety or personal endangerment provoked by the out-group, explicitly or implicitly present.

Economics	The utterance centres the problem described in its narrative on economical issues that are a consequence of the actions of the out-group and presents an inconvenience for the in-group.
Threat to culture	The utterance centres the problem on the incompatibility of foreign cultures with western culture or expresses anxieties about an alleged replacement/safety threat/cultural invasion of the country. Sometimes, the text could refer to religion, poor integration of migrant communities due to language, clothes or food traditions, or attacked and targeted for being uncivilised/barbaric. Sometimes, the utterance could defend existential cultural incompatibilities between the in-group and out-group.
Invisibilization of the woman	The utterance centres the problem on the fight of trans people being a step-back on women rights, defending that only “biological women” are “real women”, providing the basis for trans-exclusionary radical feminism (TERF).
Threat to traditional gender constructs	The utterance centres the problem on the risk of losing the traditional role of men and privileges in society as well as the traditional masculinity (e.g., “being attacked by feminism”). The utterance could also be aggressive towards women who do not accept traditional roles of care-takers or housewives, who represent a threat to traditional values (including patriarchy and traditional masculinity), as well as men who do not follow traditional masculinist attitudes (the man as the protector and guide of the woman). In a similar way, the utterance may praise women who do follow traditional gender roles. This tag also grasps the anti-trans sentiment.
Threat to traditional family	The utterance centres the problem on non-traditional/normative families being an existential threat to the traditional family model (wife and husband with kids).
Own-body decision rights	The utterance centres the problem on the question of own-body decisions like the right of abortion, prostitution or surrogate pregnancy.
Ideologization of knowledge	The utterance centres the problem on the alleged ideologization of all mainstream knowledge, criticising the mainstream science (institutions), sometimes accusing scientific knowledge of being used to push an agenda or presenting the government as a dictatorship forcing this “ideologized” knowledge upon everyone. The utterance could endorse its own visions of knowledge like politically motivated revisionism or suggesting alternative take on prevailing scientific narrative (e.g., anti-vaccine movements).
Distrust of institutions	The utterance centres the problem on the role of traditional institutions, NGOs, the traditional media or the public institutions procedures like democratic elections, the legitimacy of the government or the corruption of the judiciary system. This includes also utterances that are defamatory,

	e.g., when some false accusation is created against some institution or institution-representing person 'X person is a paedophile', just to discredit and not because of justified reasons.
Culture of efforts	The utterance centres the problem on the perceived negative effects of social justice arguing that, e.g., social justice only promotes laziness, and that workers are fully responsible for their own financial situation.
Censorship	The utterance alludes to censorship, limited freedom of speech and allegedly rigged democratic procedures, e.g., "progressive dictatorship".
META Anti-nation	The utterance clearly alludes to a number of different problematizations that target various out-groups but keeps only one in-group. The Anti-nation METAnarrative conveys the idea of who is a true member of the nation and who is not. Anything that falls outside the parameters of the in-group is not a true citizen/patriot. The only true nation is the one the in-group has conceived. An example of a problematization they describe would be the one known as the "Fall of Europe" or the "Fall of the West", supported by conspiracy theories such as "The Great Replacement". Furthermore, the annotator may find that the utterance establishes a link with the "Natural order of things" narrative. This narrative describes what is perceived to be the only acceptable way of living, usually appealing to religion or "true science" as an authority to justify this vision and attack what is called "gender ideology" or the "vaccine dictatorship". People that don't fit into this vision of the nation are usually deemed as Cultural Marxists (see explanation under US/them dichotomy above). Because of the category's particularities, when this tag is used, it is then linked to the "META" tag also under Variation and Perspective.
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Variation

This category aims to indicate the exact variation of the problematization described in the selected text.

VALUE	DESCRIPTION
Rape	The utterance makes a relation between a specific out-group and the risk of rape and shows hostility to the mentioned out-group.
Robbery	The utterance makes a relation between a specific out-group and the risk of robbery and shows hostility to the mentioned out-group.

Murder	The utterance makes a relation between a specific out-group and the risk of murder and shows hostility to the mentioned out-group.
Illegal Selling	The utterance stigmatises and is hostile towards particular individuals or groups for illegally selling on the streets.
Health Hazard	The utterance shows concern for the health of an individual or group, sometimes stigmatising and showing hostility to certain out-groups as carriers of diseases or supporting conspiracy theories about environmental health hazards like 5G or “chemtrails”.
Stealing jobs	The utterance shows hostility towards a specific out-group, mainly migrants or foreigners, accusing them of stealing the jobs of the nationals.
Exploitation of the social system	The utterance shows hostility towards a specific out-group, mainly migrants or foreigners, accusing them of planning to exploit the system benefits, e.g., economical subsidies or healthcare.
Religion	The utterance shows hostility towards a specific or multiple religious groups, usually targeting Islam.
Lack of integration	The utterance shows hostility towards groups, usually migrants, that keep their traditions or are not fully integrated in the ones of the welcoming country.
Inappropriate clothes	The utterance shows hostility to a certain group for the clothes they wear.
Inappropriate behaviour	The utterance stigmatises a certain group as uncivilised or not fit to live amongst the members of the in-group because of their alleged behaviour.
Trans-fight is threatening women's rights	The utterance argues that defending trans rights means to invisibilize the “biological” women and that policies that favour transgender people are a danger to “real women” who will be substituted by “men dressed up”, losing all the rights won by the feminist fight. This applies to traditional jobs, as well as sporting competitions where transgender women are allowed to compete with cis women.
Feminism is going too far	The utterance presents the narrator as allegedly in favour of feminism, but criticising the current state of the feminist movement, arguing that it has gone too far.
Against-men policies	The utterance shows hostility to the feminist movement and argues that feminism does not seek to fight for women's rights, but to destroy the traditional white heterosexual men, actively promoting policies against men.

The loss of the true/good woman	The utterance argues that there are almost no true/good women left, criticising women who freely enjoy their sexuality, e.g., body count, or that don't follow the traditional gender roles of care-takers and housewives, e.g., sport women.
The loss of the true man	The utterance conveys the idea that the men in question are not true men anymore because they do not follow the traditional gender role of providers and macho patriachs.
Machismo/misogyny	Machismo emphasizes strict gender roles and promotes unequal opportunities between men and women, while misogyny is a more overt expression of hostility, discrimination, and violence toward women. This tag should be used for straight up incel/misogynists tweets when the other tags, like the loss of the true woman, do not fit.
Homosexual marriage	The utterance shows disapproval of same-sex marriage, presenting it as a threat to traditional family values.
Adoption for homosexual families	The utterance is against the right of adoption for homosexual families, arguing, for example, that the family is composed of a male father, a female mother, and their children.
Abortion	The utterance is against the right to abortion.
Surrogate pregnancy	The utterance is about the right to surrogate pregnancy.
In vitro	The utterance is about the right to in vitro fertilisation.
Prostitution	The utterance is about the right to prostitution.
Science as an absolute authority	The utterance accuses, for example, the government of using science as an absolute truth to impose elements like vaccines against your will, presenting the public institution as a form of dictatorship or danger/threat to the human race. The utterance will accuse institutions/individuals/"globalists powers" of pushing certain scientific knowledge to justify a particular political agenda that benefits the globalist elites like the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.
Trivialization of totalitarian ideologies/regimes	The utterance downplays the role of totalitarian regimes or ideologies like fascism in order to whitewash it and promote it, usually supporting the arguments with politically motivated historical revisionism.
Distrust of media	The utterance shows hostility against traditional or "legacy" media, accusing them of not being trustworthy or honest with the truth, and may

	promote other ways of informing themselves with unverified or unchecked online blogs.
Distrust of science	The utterance shows hostility against science institutions or science itself.
Distrust of government/democracy	The utterance shows hostility against the public government institutions, questioning its legitimacy or doubting democratic procedures like elections. It conveys the idea of the government wanting to control the opinions and behaviour of the citizens, sometimes calling out a "dictatorship of progressivism", accusing the elected government/public institutions of tyrants or anti-democrats.
Meritocracy	The utterance defends the notion that everyone belongs to the social class they deserve without taking into consideration inherited social/economical inequalities, defending that everything depends on you alone.
Laziness in social progress	The utterance defends the notion that social justice equals or promotes the laziness of the people, defending that social justice policies are bad for the growth of society.
Toxic stoicism	The utterance defends that a particular individual facing a difficult situation should not complain nor try to solve it, but ignore it and keep going, not attending to the emotions derived from the particular situation. It promotes a cold, unempathetic and emotionless way of living, usually associated with toxic masculinity. It also promotes uncomplaining endurance.
Loss of national/regional independence	The utterance shows concern about the loss of national sovereignty to supranational institutions like the UN, NATO, WHO, etc. and the so called "globalists powers/elites". It also includes utterances that show loss of independence of certain regions to the national government.
Invasion of the country/west	The utterance shows concern about an alleged racial/ethnic/cultural invasion of the own country or of the west as a whole.
Change in education	The utterance shows concern about changes in the educational system or syllabus due to the out-group and includes utterances that warn about indoctrination of children.
META	Only when METAnarrative is used under problematization.
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Perspective

This category is used to identify the general attitude or the underlying ideology that, explicitly or implicitly, motivates the author of the text.

VALUE	DESCRIPTION
EU human rights advocacy	The utterance is aligned with values such as religious, ethnic or cultural pluralism, feminism and general support to human rights.
Religious integralism	The utterance defends the salience of religious principles in society and politics having a strict/fundamentalist adherence to sacred texts. Religious principles are seen as important and used in argumentation in politics and societal management.
Illiberalism	The utterance doubts standard democratic procedures, e.g., hindering free elections, not accepting the results, suggesting coup d'état, or disregards its democratic institutions. Illiberals accuse a democratically elected government of instauring a dictatorship or erasing the separation of powers.
Ethnonationalism	The utterance supports the national/regional homogeneity regarding language, religion and genetics. It combines nationalism and xenophobia.
Anti-communism	The utterance opposes the economic premises of communism.
Science sceptics	The utterance promotes stance against official mainstream science and defends the alternative studies as the true ones, e.g., discredits official covid studies and vaccines or promoting dubious drug protocols) or fully rejects all scientific inquiry, e.g., creationism, mental illness denialists.
Patriarchy	The utterance centres the society around male experience and privilege or/and praises women who accept the traditional role of care-taker/housewife, implicitly or explicitly diminishing or disapproving of women who break the traditional roles.
Heteronormativity	The utterance defends that heterosexuality is the default and appropriate sex orientation, providing the basis for homophobia.
Cisnormativity	The utterance defends that the gender identity of a person is aligned with the assigned gender at birth, based on biological characteristics providing the basis for transphobia.
Ideological revisionism	The utterance challenges established facts of the past to fit a determined political purpose and push an agenda.

META	Only when METAnarrative is used under problematization.
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